

Enhance electrochemical performance of $\text{LiLa}_{0.1}\text{Mn}_{1.9}\text{O}_4$ by graphene oxide coating for lithium ion battery

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Abstract : LiMn_2O_4 doped with La^{3+} , which acts as cathode material for the test battery, was coated graphene oxide (GO) and then tested by X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron micrographs (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) for analysis of its structure and surface morphology. Its electrochemical performance was evaluated by electrochemical impedance spectra (EIS), cyclic voltammetry (CV) and charge-discharge test. Results showed that the samples which carries less impedance and larger reversible capacity than the raw material have spinel structure coated 15 nm thickness of GO. Based on this result, it can be concluded that GO, the coating material, contributes to improving the battery in its charge-discharge property and cycle performance. Besides, it is also found that the specific discharge capacity of the coating material was 125 mA hg^{-1} at 0.2C for the first time while 94.62% of its specific discharge capacity is maintained at 0.5C after 60 cycles.

Keywords : Lithium ion battery, graphene oxide, specific capacity, cycleability.

Introduction

Lithium ion batteries are widely used in many fields like transportation, aviation, military and micro-electromechanics because of their large capacity, high energy density, safety, environment-friendly and no memory effect and so on. On the other side, the manganese-base materials used in lithium ion batteries have become the most promising materials because they are available, safe and non-toxic¹⁻⁵. However, the development of lithium ion batteries is greatly limited due to the weakness in high temperature charge-discharge performance. The reasons for the weakness are as follows⁶⁻¹⁶ : (1) in the preparation, the raw materials insufficiently mixed may lead to impurity, Mn_3O_4 , in the product, (2) in the late of discharge, on the surface of intense Mn^{3+} starts the disproportionation reaction : $2\text{Mn}^{3+}(\text{s}) \rightarrow \text{Mn}^{4+}(\text{s}) + \text{Mn}^{2+}(\text{l})$. In this reaction, the generated Mn^{2+} dissolves in the electrolyte, which prevents the reversible reaction from proceeding, (3) Jahn-Teller effect contributes to destructing the structure of the LMO, (4) the low

conductivity of the LiMn_2O_4 (LMO) leads to difficulties in deintercalation of Li^+ .

To solve all these problems, this experiment focuses on two major aspects : doping¹⁷⁻²¹ and coating²²⁻³⁴. On the one hand, the dissolution of Mn^{2+} and volatilization of the electrolyte are to be realized by substituting part of Mn^{3+} in order to slow down Jahn-Teller effect by improving electric conductivity of the battery. On the other hand, reduce the self-discharge efficiency of the battery by decreasing its internal resistance to make it easier for Li^+ to intercalate and deintercalate between positive and negative electrodes.

In this paper, the electrochemical performances of $\text{LiLa}_{0.1}\text{Mn}_{1.9}\text{O}_4$ (LLMO) coated by GO are reported. The synthetic samples are characterized by XRD, SEM, TEM, EIS, CV and charge-discharge test for study on its structure, surface morphology and electrochemical performance. According to the results, the coated materials improve the battery in its morphology, charge-discharge performance and cycle performance.

Experimental

Chemical agent :

Expanded graphite (Laboratory Reagent (LR) pure), sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) (analytical reagent (AR) pure), potassium permanganate (K_2MnO_4) (AR pure), H_2O_2 (AR pure), lithium acetate ($\text{Li}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (AR pure), manganous acetate ($\text{Mn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (AR pure), lanthanum chloride (LaCl_3) (AR pure), polyethylene glycol (PEG) (AR pure), *N*-methylpyrrolidinone (NMP) (AR pure), conductive carbon black (LR pure), polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) (LR pure), ethylene carbonate (EC) (AR pure), dimethyl carbonate (DMC) (AR pure).

Oxide graphene (GO) preparation :

The GO^{35} was prepared by mixing the 1 g expanded graphite, 200 ml H_2SO_4 and 10 g K_2MnO_4 into a three-necked bottle and mixed uniformly. After a 60 °C water-bath heating, the bottle was put into a magnetic stir for 24 h, the mix becoming thick black. 200 ml deionized water was slowly added into the bottle, mixed uniformly and then 50 ml H_2O_2 was added. After a 10 min centrifugal stir, the mix turned thick and gray to transparent and orange. The mix was conditioned under acid pickling for 3 times and then water-washing twice at a centrifugal rate of 12000 times per second.

Preparation of spinel LLMO :

$\text{Li}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})$, $\text{Mn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ and LaCl_3 (mass ratio of Li, Mn, La kept at 1.3 : 1.9 : 0.1) were mixed uniformly (extra lithium was added for its consumption in preparation) and fully grounded, the mix was preheated within a atmosphere furnace for 4 h at 450 °C below a heating rate of 10 °C min^{-1} . After furnace cooling, the mix was reheated at 750 °C for 50 h below a heating rate of 10 °C min^{-1} . Then furnace cooling again, black cathode material was obtained.

Synthesis of GO-coated LLMO and battery assembly :

GO-coated LLMO cathode material were synthesized using PEG process at 0, 0.2 and 0.4 wt.% with GO used as the coating of raw material. PEG (0.112 g) was dissolved in NMP (3 mL) with 1 h of warm baths, added the GO which was calculation of 0, 0.2 and 0.4 wt.% and labeled with a, b, c. The mixture was stirring for 2 h at room temperature. Then added dropwise to the dispersed LLMO (1.12 g). Thus obtained mixture was dried in an air at 100 °C for 30 h. The GO-coated LLMO cathode

materials were obtained.

PVDF (0.14 g) was dissolved in NMP (3 mL), conductive agent (conductive carbon black) (0.14 g) and GO-coated LLMO cathode materials were mixed in NMP and made into homogeneous slurry. The GO-coated LLMO electrode were prepared by roll-pressing a mixed paste of slurry into thick film and pressing the electrode film onto aluminum net. diaphragm Celgard2300 microporous membrane as separator and 1 mol^{-1} LiPF_6 in ethylene carbonate (EC)/dimethyl carbonate (DMC) (1 : 1, in wt.%) as electrolyte, the battery assembly work was completed within an argon-filled hand box.

Results and discussion

Analysis of X-ray diffraction (XRD) :

The morphology of the powders was characterized by XRD spectra (DX-2700) with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation sources (1.5406 Å) from 10–90° at a scanning rate of 0.03° s^{-1} . Fig. 1 shows the X-ray diffraction patterns of LMO, LLMO and coated materials. It is found that the diffraction peaks at $2\theta = 19.19^\circ$, 36.41° , 37.91° , 44.90° , 48.31° , 58.2° , 64.82° and 68.94° are relative to the crystal planes of (1 1 1), (3 1 1), (2 2 2), (4 0 0), (3 3 1), (5 1 1), (4 4 0) and (5 3 1). All powders had spinel structure with

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of LMO and LLMO powers.

Table 1. Average lattice constants and FWHMs at (400)

Group	A (LMO)	B (LLMO)
Lattice parameter (Å)	8.25	8.23
Unit cell volume (Å^3)	561.5	557.4
FWHM 400 (°)	0.1694	0.1603
Composition though ICP-AES	$\text{Li}_{1.12}\text{Mn}_{1.89}\text{O}_{3.98}$	$\text{Li}_{1.09}\text{La}_{0.14}\text{Mn}_{1.88}\text{O}_{3.94}$

a $\text{Fd } \bar{3}m$ space group of cubic structure (JCPDS No. 35-0782). It can be found from the figure that no La^{3+} and spinel structure was detected in samples from the two groups, which may result from a shortage of La^{3+} source. The chemical composition of the sample was analyzed by inductively coupled plasma-atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES). The compositions of the LMO and LLMO were determined to be $\text{Li}_{1.12}\text{Mn}_{1.89}\text{O}_{3.98}$ and $\text{Li}_{1.09}\text{La}_{0.14}\text{Mn}_{1.88}\text{O}_{3.94}$. The GO coating has not changed the 2θ value of the peaks. These results revealed that the GO coating is different from La^{3+} doping³⁶. Fig. 1 shows the average lattice constant and the FWHM at the (400) crystal plane from samples, from which it can be found that both the average lattice constant and lattice size of the sample decreased after it was doped with La^{3+} . This probably resulted from the addition of La^{3+} replacing part of Mn^{3+} . As La-O has stronger bond energy than Mn-O, the lattice shrank. Because the FWHM at the (400) crystal plane became smaller, the degree of crystallinity of sample went up, which made it more stable in chemistry reaction within the battery and allowed the reversible reaction to proceed normally.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and test of transmission electron microscopy (TEM) :

The morphology of group b was tested using SEM (EVO18) with a microscope magnification of 10000X at a voltage of 20.0 kV and TEM (JEOLJEM2100). Fig. 2 shows the SEM and TEM of LLMO coated with 2 wt. %

Fig. 2. The SEM and TEM images of the 2 wt. % GO-coated LLMO : (a, b) SEM; (c, d) TEM.

GO. From (a) and (b), it can be known that the sample is smooth spherical structure with a grain size of 300–900 nm and no protuberance was observed on its surface; from (c) and (d), it can be found that the sample was coated with a some 15 nm thickness of GO, which reduced the contact between cathode material and the electrolyte and upgraded the conductivity of the material. Electron diffraction spectroscopy (EDS) was applied to determine the element of LMO and LLMO samples. The images are shown in Fig. 3. Au element is detected because of sample was sprayed gold processing. La element cannot be observed in Fig. 3(a), and La element can be detected in Fig. 3(b). This indicated that La element doesn't exist in pristine LMO and it exist in LLMO.

Electrochemical impedance spectra (EIS) analysis :

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy was studied with a frequency range of 10 MHz–100 KHz and amplitude of 5 mV. Fig. 4 was the EIS plots of three groups in initial charge process. It was found that in three groups, mediate-frequency area presented semi-circle curves while in high frequency area radial oblique lines were observed. Sample coated with 4 wt. % GO was found to have least the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}), least internal resistance and lowest self-discharge efficiency³⁷. This probably caused by the GO coating, which changed the conductivity of cathode material and made it easier for Li^+ to intercalate and deintercalate.

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) study :

Cyclic voltammetry curve was studied at electrochemical workstation with an initial potential of 3.2 V and a maximum of 4.4 V. Scanning rate was 0.1 mV s^{-1} with a sensitivity of $1 \times e^{-0.04}$ and test temperature of 15 °C. The contrast electrodes and auxiliary electrode were lithium electrode. Fig. 5 showed the cyclic voltammetry curve of three groups. Samples from the three groups, all corresponding to two redox peaks wick locate at 4.13 V/4.00 V, 4.01 V/3.89 V for group a electrode, 4.18 V/4.05 V, 4.02 V/3.89 V for group b electrode and 4.18 V/4.05 V, 4.00 V/3.81 V for group c electrode. Intercalation and deintercalation of Li^+ are detected great growth in peak current after being coated, which promotes the heavy load charge-discharge performance for the battery.

Fig. 3. The EDS spectrum of samples : (a) LMO, (b) LLMO.

Fig. 4. EIS plots of three groups in initial charge process : (a) 0 wt.% GO, (b) 2 wt.% GO, (c) 4 wt.% GO.

Fig. 6. Charge-discharge curves of three groups and LMO sample at 0.2C in the voltage range of 3.20–4.35 V vs Li/Li⁺ : (a) 0 wt.% GO, (b) 2 wt.% GO, (c) 4 wt.% GO.

Fig. 5. First cyclic voltammograms of three groups. Scan rate : 0.1 mV s⁻¹; (a) 0 wt.% GO, (b) 2 wt.% GO, (c) 4 wt.% GO.

Fig. 7. Cycling curves of three groups and LMO sample at 0.5C in the voltage range of 3.20–4.35V vs Li/Li⁺ : (a) 0 wt.% GO, (b) 2 wt.% GO, (c) 4 wt.% GO.

The chemical diffusion coefficient of Li⁺ ion (D_{Li^+}) is an important factor to influence the kinetic of the elec-

trode materials. The D_{Li^+} can be calculated from eq. (1)³⁷.

$$I^P = (2.69 \times 10^5) z^{3/2} A D_{\text{Li}^+}^{1/2} C^0 v^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where I^P , z , A , D_{Li^+} and C^0 are peak current (A), the charge-transfer number, the electrode area (cm^2), the chemical diffusion coefficient ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) and the bulk concentration of Li^+ ions³⁸. $I^P = (2.69 \times 10^5) z^{3/2} A D_{\text{Li}^+}^{1/2} C^0 v^{1/2} \rightarrow I_a^P / I_b^P = A_a D_{\text{Li}^+}^{1/2} / A_b D_{\text{Li}^+}^{1/2} (C_a^0 = C_b^0 = 0.02378 \text{ mol cm}^{-3})$, ($v_a = v_b = 0.1 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$) $\rightarrow D_{\text{Li}^+}^{1/2a} / D_{\text{Li}^+}^{1/2b} = I_a^P A_b / I_b^P A_a$. The $D_{\text{Li}^+}^{1/2a}$ is greater than $D_{\text{Li}^+}^{1/2b}$. And for the same reason, the $D_{\text{Li}^+}^{1/2b}$ is greater than $D_{\text{Li}^+}^{1/2c}$. The results implied that the sample of GO coated LLMO would have a better rate capability than LLMO³⁸.

Analysis of charging-discharging :

Charge-discharge tests were performed galvanostatically at a current rate of 0.2C and 0.5C with cut-off voltages of 3.00–4.35 V at room temperature. Figs. 6 and 7 profiled the initial charge-discharge curves at 0.2C and cycling curves of three groups and LMO sample at 0.5C. It showed from Fig. 5 that the charge and discharge specific capacity of samples coated with 2% GO respectively was 135 mA hg^{-1} , 125 mA hg^{-1} at 0.2C, 135 mA hg^{-1} , 125 mA hg^{-1} with 4% GO and 114 mA hg^{-1} , 107 mA hg^{-1} with no GO. After LMO doping La^{3+} , specific discharge capacity for the first time slightly increased and the circulation property had no change. Compared with LMO that was coated with Cr_2O_3 by Halil¹⁷, the specific discharge capacity reached 118 mA hg^{-1} for the first time while maintained 102 mA hg^{-1} after 60 cycles. b showed that reversible capacity of LLMO coated by GO was higher than that of LMO coated by Cr_2O_3 . It suggested from Fig. 6 that the cathode material without coating dropped a lot in capacity while its discharge specific capacity maintained 91 mA hg^{-1} and 81.25% after 60 cycles. Samples coated with 2% GO was 105 mA hg^{-1} with a capacity retention of 81.25% after 60 cycles, samples with 4% GO was 107 mA hg^{-1} with a capacity retention of 92.10% after 60 cycles. By comparison to these results, coat material upgraded the charge-discharge performance and cycle property of the battery. A possible reason for this result is that the coat material obstructed the dissolution of Mn^{2+} and slowed down the Jahn-Teller effect.

Conclusions

Results from XRD, SEM and TEM on GO-coated and La^{3+} doped LiMn_2O_4 showed that the coated samples were spherical shape with a grain size of 400 nm, which had spinel structure; doping of La^{3+} upgraded the crystallinity of samples; material coated with GO was found to have increased electrochemical performance with greatly less impedance, less self-discharge with enhanced reversible capacity and refined cycle performance, specific discharge capacity of the coated material was 125 mA hg^{-1} for the first time at 0.2C, its capacity retention was 92.10% at 0.5C after 60 cycles.

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